

Is there a relationship between the carbon content of microbial biomass and soil organic matter parameters in clear-cut soils of the taiga zone?

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Microbial biomass is an important component of soil organic matter. Their parameters can be good indicators of soil quality and the quality of the natural environment. This study examines the relationship between soil microbial community parameters and soil organic matter characteristics in forest ecosystems transformed by clear-cutting. The research was conducted in the middle taiga subzone of the European North-East of Russia (Komi Republic). The key plots are represented by a native bilberry-green moss spruce forest (plot KE) and three derivative phytocenoses formed after clear-cutting: site PP 0 (clear-cut in 2017-2018), PP 2 (2001-2002), and PP 3 (1969-1970). The total carbon content (TOC) in the samples was assessed using a CHNS-O analyzer, and the carbon content of organic compounds in aqueous extracts (WSOC) was determined using the high-temperature catalytic oxidation method using a VCPH TOC analyzer [3] at the Collective Use Center «Chromatography» of the Institute of Biology of the Komi Scientific Center of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Microbial community parameters (basal respiration and microbial biomass carbon) were determined using the substrate-induced respiration (SIR) method.

As a result of the research conducted, the following was established:

1) Carbon stocks in the organogenic horizon of the podzolic soil of the plot KE are 2.4 ± 0.5 kg/m², in the eluvial horizon (top 5 cm) – 1.83 ± 0.28 kg/m². In the first years after clear-cutting, carbon stocks in the upper horizons increase by 1.4-2.2 times. During natural reforestation, C reserves gradually decrease, and in plot PP 3 (50 years after clear-cutting), carbon stocks in the organogenic horizons are 1.9-3.4 times lower than in plot KE, and in the mineral horizons, they are 1.5-2.7 times lower.

2) In the soil of plot KE, the share of water-soluble carbon (WSOC) in the TOC pool is 1.8-1.9%. In plot PP 0, the share of S_{vob} decreases to 1.3%, but during further natural reforestation, the share of WSOC increases to 2.1% (PP2) and 2.3% (PP3). In the eluvial horizons, the share of WSOC decreases by 1.7-2.2 times.

3) The minimum values of microbial biomass carbon (C_{mic}) were recorded in the organogenic soil horizons at plots PP 0 and PP 2 (2129-5058 µg C/g soil). At plots KE and PP 3, C_{mic} was 7030 and 8523 µg C/g soil, respectively. In the eluvial horizons of all soils, C_{mic} values decreased by an order of magnitude and averaged 268.4 (KE), 438.6 (PP 0), 481.7 (PP 2), and 644.5 (PP 3) µg C/g soil.

4) The maximum values of basal respiration (BR) were established in the organogenic horizons of the KE plot (40.9 µg C-CO₂ / g of soil), in the PP 0, PP 2 and PP 3 plots this indicator averaged 19.5, 28.3 and 32.9 µg C-CO₂ / g of soil, respectively. In the mineral horizons, a trend of increasing BR is observed in the direction: KE → PP 2 → PP 3 → PP 0.

5) The parameter that most closely correlates with the characteristics of microbial communities is the content and stocks of WSOC – the relationship between WSOC and C_{mic} is characterized by the value $r = 0.76$ ($p = 0.95$), between WSOC and BD – $r = 0.67$. In the eluvial horizons of the studied podzolic soils, correlation dependencies between the parameters of microbial communities and the parameters of soil organic matter were not revealed.

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